

Student Work

July 21, 2021

Application of Compressed Sensing Algorithms in Multipath Interference of Time-of-Flight Imaging

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Abstract

A Time-of-Flight(ToF) camera is a compact device, which can provide highly-resolved depth information between camera and scenery. However, on account of multipath interference (MPI), distortion in the measurements appears, leading to an erroneous depth estimate. A possible solution for resolving this issue is by means of algorithms that exploit sparse regularization to recover multiple return paths from multiple frequency measurements. In this paper, three different sparse reconstruction algorithms, namely, Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) and l_1 -minimization approaches like Kalman filter and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm are applied on real data affected by MPI. All the three algorithms generate an accurate depth map, among which OMP works the fastest. In addition, the convergence-accelerated algorithms of Kalman filter and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm are adopted, the depth map generated by the convergence-accelerated Kalman filter shows the smaller error areas in comparison with the other four algorithms.

1 Introduction

Compressed sensing (CS) is a signal processing technique to reconstruct a signal from a series of sampling measurements. It breaks the limit of the traditional Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem. CS requires fewer samples and is based on the principle that many signals can be represented using only a few non-zero coefficients in a suitable basis or dictionary.

A Time-of-Flight (ToF) camera is a depth image sensor. The distance information between the sensor and the objects can be obtained through the phase shift between the transmitted light and the reflected light. However, multipath interference occurs when light from a transmitter arrives at a receiver via two or more paths. Each path will produce a different phase shift, and the measurement is influenced by the individual phase shifts of each path, which leads to the incorrect phase estimation. Therefore, in order to acquire the correct depth information of a complete scene, a method of resolving MPI is by means of a CS framework, which retrieves depth information from a set of measurements at different frequencies.

Bhandari et al. addressed the MPI via the sparse recovery algorithm OMP. With 77 frequency measurements they retrieved 2 and 3 different depths [1]. Patil et al. later modified OMP algorithm. Moreover, the number of modulation frequencies is optimized to five and the depth domain is discretized into 2048 steps. The result is very close to the former with 77 modulation frequencies [2].

In this paper, apart from the OMP algorithm, the Kalman filter and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm are applied on real data effected by MPI. Using seven frequency measurements from 0 to 120 MHz, with modulation frequencies spaced 20 MHz apart, the multipath problem is solved. The depth discretization is decreased to 150, which reduces the computational complexity. In Section 4 the three algorithms are evaluated via Donoho-Tanner graphs. Furthermore, the performance of the three recovery algorithms is compared via the depth and amplitude maps generated from most prominent bounce in Section 5.

2 Principle of sparse recovery ToF data

A ToF device consists of two components, a source, e.g., LED/LASER, and a sensor. The Time-of-Flight principle is a method for measuring the distance between a sensor and an object of each pixel, based on the time difference between the emission of light signals and their reflection to the sensor. For the direct ToF camera a pulsed laser is emitted from the source, a very high frequency of the clocking signal is required to record the time information. In other words, millimeter resolution in depth requires picosecond resolution in the time. It is neither easy nor economical to achieve. In light of this reason, continuous-wave (CW) modulated signal is applied in the ToF. It is an indirect method to obtain distance information according to measure the phase shift of the reflected signal. When the experiment only has one target object, the mathematical representation of the original modulated light signal $s(t)$ and reflected signal $r(t)$ is:

$$s(t) = 1 + a \cdot \cos(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

$$r(t) = A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B \quad (2)$$

Where A and B are the unknown amplitude and offset of the reflected signal, respectively. ϕ is a scene-dependent phase shift, and $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, where f is modulation frequency. Besides, the phase shift and modulation frequency are related to the distance d via the relation:

$$d = c\phi/2\omega \quad (3)$$

Here, c is the speed of light. The pixel measures the cross-correlation between reflected signal $r(t)$ and the reference $s(t)$ [3], and samples at the time τ_q :

$$\begin{aligned} C_{r,s}(\tau_q) &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T r^*(t) s(t + \tau_q) dt \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T [A \cos(\omega t - \phi) + B] [1 + a \cdot \cos(\omega t + \omega \tau_q)] dt \\ &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T [A a \cos(\omega t - \phi) \cos(\omega t + \omega \tau_q) + B] dt \\ &= \frac{Aa}{2} \cos(\omega \tau_q + \phi) + B \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

With the help of “four-bucket” sampling [4], namely, $\tau_q = \pi q/2\omega$ with $q = 0, \dots, 3$. the amplitude A , the phase shift ϕ and the offset B of the single-pixel measurement are obtained:

$$A = \sqrt{(C(\tau_3) - C(\tau_1))^2 + (C(\tau_0) - C(\tau_2))^2} / a \quad (5)$$

$$\phi = \arctan \left[\frac{C(\tau_3) - C(\tau_1)}{C(\tau_0) - C(\tau_2)} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$B = \frac{C(\tau_0) + C(\tau_1) + C(\tau_2) + C(\tau_3)}{4} \quad (7)$$

Thereby, a pixel measurement with phasor representation and regardless of the offset reads:

$$y_\omega = A e^{j\phi(\omega)} \quad (8)$$

Provided that the experiment has K target objects, K reflections lead to a single measurement. With this in mind, the received signal $r(t)$ in phasor representation follows:

$$r(t) = K \cdot B + \frac{a}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} A_k e^{j(\omega t - \phi_k(\omega))} \quad (9)$$

Here $K \cdot B$ is constant, the corresponding time delay is computed as, $\phi(\omega) = 2d_k\omega/c$, and $\{d_k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$ are K different distances from the sensor to the target object. Then the sample of a single-pixel is obtained:

$$C_{r,s}(\tau_q) = \frac{a}{2} e^{j\omega\tau_q} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} A_k e^{j\phi_k(\omega)} + B_0 \quad (10)$$

where B_0 is constant. When the frequency ω is fixed, $C_{r,s}(\tau_q)$ is only dependent on the $e^{j\omega\tau_q}$, the components of the reflected signal $\{A_k(\omega), \phi_k(\omega)\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$ remain unchanged. Therefore, regardless of the sampling density and constant term, the phasor representation of a pixel measurement with K reflections can be simplified to:

$$y_\omega = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} A_k(\omega) e^{j\phi_k(\omega)} \quad (11)$$

The K reflection components can be separated by illuminating the scene by equally-spaced frequencies $\omega = n\omega_0 (n \in \mathbb{N})$, and an array of simplified measurements can be represented as \vec{y} :

$$\vec{y} = [y_{0\omega_0}, y_{1\omega_0}, \dots, y_{(N-1)\omega_0}]^\top \quad (12)$$

The vector \vec{y} can be expressed as $\vec{y} = \mathbf{\Phi} \vec{x}' + \vec{\sigma}$, here $\mathbf{\Phi} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times K}$:

$$\mathbf{\Phi} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{j0\phi_1} & e^{j0\phi_2} & \dots & e^{j0\phi_K} \\ e^{j1\phi_1} & e^{j1\phi_2} & \dots & e^{j1\phi_K} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ e^{j(N-1)\phi_1} & e^{j(N-1)\phi_2} & \dots & e^{j(N-1)\phi_K} \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$\vec{x}' = [A_0, \dots, A_{(K-1)}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times 1}$, and $\vec{\sigma}$ is Gaussian independent and identically distributed noise having zero mean.

In order to recover the reflection amplitude vector \vec{x}' , the similarity between $\mathbf{\Phi}$ and an oversampled discrete Fourier transform (DFT) matrix $\mathbf{\Psi} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$, with elements $\Psi_{nl} = \exp(jn2\pi l/L)$, should be firstly paid attention to. In case $L \gg K$, furthermore, every columns of $\mathbf{\Phi}$ can be approximately found in $\mathbf{\Psi}$, then a sparse vector $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$, which has only K non-zero components taken from \vec{x}' , can be defined:

$$\vec{x}_{T_0} = \vec{x}' \quad (14)$$

$$T_0 = \{i : x_i \neq 0\} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \#T_0 = K \quad (15)$$

In this experiment, seven frequency measurements are used to recover two paths, and depth domain is discretized into 150. The selected DTF matrix with 7 rows and 150 columns satisfies Restricted Isometry Property (RIP) [5]. Therefore, the \vec{y} can be anew represented as:

$$\vec{y} = \mathbf{\Psi} \vec{x} \quad (16)$$

3 Sparse reconstruction algorithm

3.1 Compressed Sensing

The goal of compressed sensing is to find a sparse solution to an underdetermined system. The underdetermined system can be mathematically represented as:

$$\vec{y} = \Psi \vec{x} \quad (17)$$

where \vec{y} is the measurement vector, $\Psi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$ is the sensing matrix. Due to the sensing rate of $R = m/L \leq 1$, the unique recovery of \vec{x} is not possible in general cases. However, provided that the vector \vec{x} is sparse, namely, the sparsity $K < L$, then a unique solution can be computed in an overcomplete system. Here sparsity means the number of non-zero coefficients:

$$K = \|\vec{x}\|_0 := \#\{i : x_i \neq 0\} \quad (18)$$

Then the sparsity K is less than the dimension of the sparse vector L . Recovering sparse vector \vec{x} would suppose solving the following optimization problem:

$$\vec{x} = \arg \min \|\vec{x}\|_0 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \vec{y} = \Psi \vec{x} \quad (19)$$

Though the result is accurate via l_0 minimization, the computational process is an NP problem [6]. A method to address this issue is to relax the l_0 minimization into an l_1 minimization:

$$\vec{x} = \arg \min \|\vec{x}\|_1 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \vec{y} = \Psi \vec{x} \quad (20)$$

The Figure 1 shows the l_1 and l_2 balls touching the feasible sets in the l_1 minimization and l_2 minimization solutions, respectively. The oblique line expresses the set of all vector \vec{x} , which satisfies $\vec{y} = \Psi \vec{x}$. The two-dimensional l_1 ball is a square, and l_1 minimization is graphically to find the contact point between the solution line and the smallest square. Since the intersection is located in the coordinate axis, then the sparsity of l_1 minimization is promoted. However, for the circular shape of l_2 ball, the contact point is likely away from the coordinate axis. Therefore, compared with l_2 minimization, l_1 minimization favors sparse solutions.

Figure 1: l_1 and l_2 ball

3.2 Orthogonal Matching Pursuit

Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) [7] is one kind of greedy iterative algorithm, which makes the best choice at each step in order to find the optimal solution of the entire problem.

The underdetermined equation (17) can be transformed into:

$$\vec{x} = \arg \min \|\vec{y} - \Psi \vec{x}\|_2^2 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \|\vec{x}\|_0 \leq K \quad (21)$$

where the matrix $\Psi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$ is an overcomplete dictionary, and $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$ is a sparse vector with the sparsity of K . Measurement vector $\vec{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times 1}$ is a sparse linear combination of atoms of dictionary Ψ .

In OMP algorithm, the best matching atom of the dictionary, which has the highest correlation with the current residual, will be selected in each iteration. Furthermore, the residual can be projected onto the orthogonal subspace spanned by the selected atoms. In general, OMP is a sparse approximation algorithm that finds an estimate of the sparse vector \vec{x} , which contains the weights associated to each atom.

Algorithm 1 Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)

Input: Dictionary Ψ , measurement vector \vec{y} , sparsity K or error ϵ .

Output: Sparse vector \vec{x}

- 1: residual: $r = \vec{y}$
 - 2: pseudoinverse of Ψ : $\text{pinv}(\Psi)$
 - 3: **for** $i \leq K$ **do**:
 - 4: $j = \arg \max |\Psi^\top r|$
 - 5: Update support: $T = T \cup j$
 - 6: Update estimate: $\vec{x}_T = \text{pinv}(\Psi_T)r$
 - 7: Update residual: $r = \vec{y} - \Psi_T \vec{x}_T$
 - 8: **end for**
-

The sparsity K in the above algorithm determines the number of iterations and the atom Ψ_j is the one showing the highest correlation with the current residual r , and the set of selected atoms Ψ_T is expanded at each step [8]. A small value ϵ can be set as external thresholding and the abort criterion is:

$$\frac{\|\vec{y} - \Psi \vec{x}\|_2}{\|\vec{y}\|_2} < \epsilon \quad (22)$$

3.3 l_1 -Minimization Kalman Filter

In Kalman filter the underdetermined equation (17) can be considered as l_1 -minimization problem:

$$\vec{x} = \arg \min \|\vec{x}\|_1 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \vec{y} = \Psi \vec{x} + \sigma \quad (23)$$

where $\Psi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$ is the observation matrix, $\vec{\sigma}$ is a noise vector, assumed to be drawn from a multivariate zero-mean Gaussian distribution with covariance R , and $\vec{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times 1}$ is the vector of measurements, which can be observed based on the state vector $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$.

3.3.1 Nullspace-Based Kalman Filter

In order to reconstruct the state vector \vec{x} via l_1 -minimization, firstly, the nullspace of the observation matrix is introduced as follows:

$$N(\Psi) := \{\vec{x} : \Psi \vec{x} = 0\} \quad (24)$$

With the help of LQ decomposition of the observation matrix Ψ , $\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} = \mathbf{Q}_2^H \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times (L-m)}$, the basis of the nullspace of observation matrix Ψ , is obtained. In addition, leveraging nullspace, the state vector \vec{x} can be decomposed into particular solution \vec{x}_p , as well as the product of the basis nullspace $\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}$

and the nonobserved vector $\vec{x}_v \in \mathbb{C}^{(L-m)}$, which can represent the full state vector \vec{x} with minimal dimension number:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{x} &= \vec{x}_p + \vec{v}_x \quad \vec{v}_x \in N(\Psi) \\ &= \vec{x}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v\end{aligned}\quad (25)$$

Here $\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v \in N(\Psi)$ represents a nullspace vector, and the particular solution x_p can be calculated via least squares (LS), which is shown in [9].

$$\vec{\hat{x}}_p = \mathbf{Q}_1^H \mathbf{L}_1^{-1} \vec{y} \quad (26)$$

The equation (23) can be transformed into:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{\hat{x}}_{opt} &= \arg \min_{\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v \in (N(\Psi) + \vec{\hat{x}}_p)} \|\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v\|_1 \\ &= \vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{Q}_2^H \arg \min_{\vec{x}_v} \|\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{Q}_2^H \vec{x}_v\|_1\end{aligned}\quad (27)$$

Instead of the full state vector \vec{x} , it is only needed to estimate the $(L - m)$ -dimensional vector \vec{x}_v .

3.3.2 Extended Kalman Filter

If the measurement noise is additive, the nonlinear measurement model can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned}y^{(k)} &= \|\vec{x}\|_1 \\ &= \|\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v\|_1 + v^{(k)} \\ &= h(\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v) + v^{(k)}\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

where the nonlinear measurement $y^{(k)}$ can be obtained according to the nonlinear function $h(\vec{x}) = \|\vec{x}\|_1$ like line 9 in Algorithm 2. The $v^{(k)}$ is the observation noise, with the covariance of \mathbf{R} .

$$y^{(k)} = \gamma^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-(k)}\|_1 \quad (29)$$

Here $\gamma^{(k)} = 1 - r^{(k)}$, and $0 < \gamma \leq 1$. The parameter: $r^{(k)} = (1 - \hat{r})r^{(k-1)}$, with initialized $r(0) \in]0, 1]$, $\hat{r} \in]0, 1]$, so that $r^{(k)}$ will tend to zero when $k \rightarrow \infty$, and $\gamma^{(k)} \rightarrow 1$.

$0 < \gamma \leq 1$ can guarantee that, the estimate of l_1 -norm can be decreased in each iteration. Then the prediction estimate is corrected to the filtered state estimate by adding the residual between new l_1 -norm and the preceding l_1 -norm weighted by the Kalman gain:

$$\vec{x}^{+(k)} = \vec{x}^{-(k)} + \mathbf{K}^{(k)} \left[y^{(k)} - \|\vec{x}^{-(k)}\|_1 \right] \quad (30)$$

In the end the error covariance of the estimate is updated as shown in line 15. Significantly, owing to the nonlinear function $h(\vec{x})$, the extended Kalman filter will be applied. On the other hand, making use of Jacobian matrix, the nonlinear function can be linearized, which is shown in line 11 of Algorithm 2. The nonlinear mapping $h(\vec{x})$ is the l_1 -norm of the complete estimate [10]:

$$h(\vec{x}^{-(k)}) = \|\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v^{-(k)}\|_1 \quad (31)$$

The l_1 -norm can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} h(\vec{x}) &= \|\vec{x}\|_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^*}{|x_i|} x_i \\ &= H(\vec{x}) \cdot \vec{x} \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Then:

$$H(\vec{x}) = \frac{dh(\vec{x})}{d\vec{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{x_1^*}{|x_1|} & \frac{x_2^*}{|x_2|} & \frac{x_3^*}{|x_3|} & \dots & \frac{x_n^*}{|x_n|} \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

where $x_i \neq 0$. According to equation (31,32,33):

$$\begin{aligned} h(\vec{x}^{-(k)}) &= H^{(k)} \left[\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v^{-(k)} \right] \\ &= H^{(k)}\vec{\hat{x}}_p + H^{(k)}\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v^{-(k)} \\ &= H^{(k)}\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{C}^{(k)}\vec{x}_v^{-(k)} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

From the equation (34), the Jacobian matrix is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}^{(k)} &= \frac{dh(\vec{\hat{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}\vec{x}_v^{-(k)})}{d\vec{x}_v^{-(k)}} \\ &= H^{(k)}\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} \\ &= \left[\frac{x_i^{-(k)}}{|x_i^{-(k)}|} \right]_{1 \leq i \leq L}^H \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Algorithm 2 l_1 -Minimizing Kalman Filter

Input: observation matrix $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$, observation vector $\vec{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1}$, $\vec{\tilde{x}}_p = \mathbf{Q}_1^H \mathbf{L}_1^{-1} \vec{y}$, $\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} = \mathbf{Q}_2^H \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times (L-m)}$.

Output: Sparsity vector \vec{x} .

- 1: **Initialize:** $\vec{x}_v^{(0)} = 0$, $\vec{x}^{+(0)} = \vec{\tilde{x}}_p$, $\mathbf{P}^{+(0)} = \mathbf{P}_0$
 - 2: **for** $\Delta \|\vec{x}_v^{(k)}\|_1 > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 3: **Prediction:**
 - 4: State: $\vec{x}_v^{-}(k) = \vec{x}_v^{+(k-1)}$
 - 5: Covariance: $\mathbf{P}^{-}(k) = \mathbf{P}^{+(k-1)}$
 - 6: State: $\vec{x}^{-}(k) = \vec{x}^{+(k-1)}$
 - 7: Parameter: $r^{-}(k) = r^{+(k-1)}$
 - 8: **Measurement update:**
 - 9: Measure: $y^{(k)} = \gamma^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1$
 - 10: Residual: $\tilde{y}^{(k)} = -r^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1$
 - 11: Jacobian matrix: $\mathbf{C}^{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} x_i^{-}(k) \\ \vdots \\ x_i^{-}(k) \end{bmatrix}_{1 \leq i \leq L}^H \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}$
 - 12: Kalman gain: $\mathbf{K}^{(k)} = \mathbf{P}^{-}(k) \mathbf{C}^{H(k)} (\mathbf{C}^{(k)} \mathbf{P}^{-}(k) \mathbf{C}^{H(k)} + R)^{-1}$
 - 13: Estimate: $\vec{x}_v^{+}(k) = \vec{x}_v^{-}(k) + \mathbf{K}^{(k)} \tilde{y}^{(k)}$
 - 14: Estimate: $\vec{x}^{+}(k) = \vec{\tilde{x}}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} \vec{x}_v^{+}(k)$
 - 15: Covariance: $\mathbf{P}^{+(k)} = \mathbf{P}^{-}(k) - \mathbf{K}^{(k)} \mathbf{C}^{(k)} \mathbf{P}^{-}(k)$
 - 16: $k = k + 1$
 - 17: **end for**
-

3.3.3 Convergence-Accelerated Kalman Filter

The Algorithm 2 does not always converge to the right solution. When the dimension of the observation matrix Ψ is small, e.g., $L = 64$, stable convergence can be obtained almost always, however, for the large dimensions, e.g., $L = 120$, not anymore. When k is large enough, $\gamma^{(k)}$ tends to be 1, the l_1 -norm does not decrease anymore, even though the minimal l_1 norm is not reached.

The Aitken's delta-squared process can be used to realize convergence-acceleration [11]. For a linearly-converging sequence u_k converging to u , when n is large:

$$\frac{u_{k+1} - u}{u_k - u} \approx \frac{u_{k+2} - u}{u_{k+1} - u} \quad (36)$$

Then a new sequence converges faster:

$$u \approx \hat{u} = u_k - \frac{(u_{k+1} - u_k)^2}{u_{k+2} - 2u_{k+1} + u_k} \quad (37)$$

The sequence \hat{u} is called Steffensen's sequence. In order to realize super-linear convergence, an extrapolation method can be used from the start of the iteration [12]:

$$\omega_k = \frac{\Delta u_{k-1}}{\Delta u_{k-1} - \Delta u_k} \quad (38)$$

$$\tilde{u}_{k+1} = u_k + \omega_k \Delta u_{k-1} \quad (39)$$

where ω_k is relaxation factor, $\Delta u_k = u_{k+1} - u_k$, $\Delta u_{k-1} = u_k - u_{k-1}$ and \tilde{u}_{k+1} is the new sequence, which converges faster than the original sequence u_k .

Then, a new convergence-accelerated algorithm is shown in Algorithm 3. After the extrapolation method, the reduced measurement \tilde{y} is calculated through Steffensen's method(line 26 of Algorithm 3), and the value \tilde{y} will converge to a limit value different from zero. Moreover, after the third iteration step, \hat{r} is obtained by Steffensen's method as well, which makes $r^{(k)}$ tend to zero when $k \rightarrow \infty$. In addition, the estimate of state \vec{x} converges to a fixed value.

On condition that the noise is nonadditive, the measurement function has the following form $h(\vec{x}, v)$, $h(\vec{x}, 0) = \|\vec{x}\|_1$. The measurement evolves as a function of the state and measurement noise. In the end the Jacobi-matrix is obtained as $\hat{I}^{(k)} = \frac{dh(\vec{x}, v)}{dv}$.

Algorithm 3 Convergence Accelerated l_1 -Minimizing Kalman Filter

Input: observation matrix $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$, observation vector $\vec{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1}$, $\vec{x}_p = \mathbf{Q}_1^H \mathbf{L}_1^{-1} \vec{y}$, $\mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} = \mathbf{Q}_2^H \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times (L-m)}$.

Output: Sparsity vector \vec{x} .

- 1: **Initialize:** $\vec{x}_v^{(0)} = 0$, $\vec{x}^{+(0)} = \vec{x}_p$, $\mathbf{P}^{+(0)} = \mathbf{P}_0$
 - 2: **for** $\Delta \|\vec{x}_v^{(k)}\|_1 > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 3: **Prediction:**
 - 4: State: $\vec{x}_v^{-}(k) = \vec{x}_v^{+(k-1)}$
 - 5: Covariance: $\mathbf{P}^{-}(k) = \mathbf{P}^{+(k-1)}$
 - 6: State: $\vec{x}^{-}(k) = \vec{x}^{+(k-1)}$
 - 7: Parameter: $r^{-}(k) = r^{+(k-1)}$
 - 8: **Measurement update:**
 - 9: Measure: $y^{(k)} = \gamma^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1$
 - 10: Residual: $\tilde{y}^{(k)} = -r^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1$
 - 11: Jacobian matrix: $\mathbf{C}^{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{x_i^{-}(k)}{\|x_i^{-}(k)\|} \end{bmatrix}_{1 \leq i \leq L}^H \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)}$
 - 12: Kalman gain: $\mathbf{K}^{(k)} = \mathbf{P}^{-}(k) \mathbf{C}^{H(k)} (\mathbf{C}^{(k)} \mathbf{P}^{-}(k) \mathbf{C}^{H(k)} + \hat{\mathbf{I}}^{(k)} \mathbf{R} \hat{\mathbf{I}}^{H(k)})^{-1}$
 - 13: Estimate: $\vec{x}_v^{+}(k) = \vec{x}_v^{-}(k) + \mathbf{K}^{(k)} \tilde{y}^{(k)}$
 - 14: Estimate: $\vec{x}^{+}(k) = \vec{x}_p + \mathbf{E}_{N(\Psi)} \vec{x}_v^{+}(k)$
 - 15: Covariance: $\mathbf{P}^{+(k)} = \mathbf{P}^{-}(k) - \mathbf{K}^{(k)} \mathbf{C}^{(k)} \mathbf{P}^{-}(k)$
 - 16: $k = k + 1$
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: (The following steps are same as the above **Prediction** and **Measurement update process**, but with the following changes)
 - 19: **if** $k=2$ **then**
 - 20: Relaxation parameter: $\omega_k = \frac{\|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1 - \|\vec{x}^{-(k-1)}\|_1}{2\|\vec{x}^{-(k)}\|_1 - \|\vec{x}^{-(k-1)}\|_1 - \|\vec{x}^{-(k+1)}\|_1}$
 - 21: Residual: $\tilde{y}^{(k)} = -r^{(k)} (\|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1 + \omega_k (\|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1 - \|\vec{x}^{-(k-1)}\|_1))$
 - 22: **else**
 - 23: **if** $k=3$ **then**
 - 24: Prediction residual : $\tilde{y}^{-(k)} = -r^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1$
 - 25: Update residual: $\tilde{y}^{(k)} = \frac{\tilde{y}^{-(k)} \tilde{y}^{(k-2)} - (\tilde{y}^{(k-1)})^2}{\tilde{y}^{-(k)} - 2\tilde{y}^{(k-1)} + \tilde{y}^{(k-2)}}$
 - 26: **else**
 - 27: **if** $k > 3$ **then**
 - 28: Update parameter: $\hat{r}^{+(k)} = \frac{r^{-(k)} r^{(k-2)} - (r^{(k-1)})^2}{r^{-(k)} - 2r^{(k-1)} + r^{(k-2)}}$
 - 29: Update parameter: $r^{(k)} = (1 - \hat{r}^{+(k)}) r^{-(k)}$
 - 30: Prediction residual : $\tilde{y}^{-(k)} = -r^{(k)} \|\vec{x}^{-}(k)\|_1$
 - 31: Update residual: $\tilde{y}^{(k)} = \frac{\tilde{y}^{-(k)} \tilde{y}^{(k-2)} - (\tilde{y}^{(k-1)})^2}{\tilde{y}^{-(k)} - 2\tilde{y}^{(k-1)} + \tilde{y}^{(k-2)}}$
 - 32: **end if**
 - 33: **end if**
 - 34: **end if**
-

3.4 Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm for l_1 -Minimization

Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm is a method to solve the non-smooth convex optimization problem. Then, by l_1 minimization, the solution of the underdetermined equation can be approached as a convex optimization problem(17):

$$\vec{x} = \arg \min_{\vec{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}} \|\vec{x}\|_1 + \frac{\gamma}{2} \|\Psi \vec{x} - \vec{y}\|_2^2 \quad (40)$$

In convex optimization the above equation can be considered into the primal problem:

$$\min_{\vec{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}} F(\Psi \vec{x}) + G(\vec{x}) \quad (41)$$

Where $F : \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1} \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$, $G : \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1} \rightarrow (-\infty, \infty]$ are proper convex and lower-semicontinuous function. The corresponding dual problem reads:

$$\max_{\vec{\xi} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1}} -F^*(\vec{\xi}) - G^*(-\Psi^H \vec{\xi}) \quad (42)$$

Here F^* and G^* are the convex conjugates of the function F and G , respectively. Based on the above primal problem or dual problem, the equivalent saddle-point problem can be obtained:

$$\min_{\vec{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}} \max_{\vec{\xi} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1}} \langle \Psi \vec{x}, \vec{\xi} \rangle + G(\vec{x}) - F^*(\vec{\xi}) \quad (43)$$

According to equation (40) and (41):

$$G(\vec{x}) = \|\vec{x}\|_1 \quad (44)$$

$$F(\Psi \vec{x}) = \frac{\gamma}{2} \|\Psi \vec{x} - \vec{y}\|_2^2 \quad (45)$$

The convex conjugate function $F^*(\vec{\xi})$ can be represented as:

$$F^*(\vec{\xi}) = \langle \vec{y}, \vec{\xi} \rangle + \frac{1}{2\gamma} \|\vec{\xi}\|_2^2 \quad (46)$$

Algorithm 4 Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

Input: $\Psi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$, $\tau, \sigma > 0$ simultaneously with $\tau\sigma L^2 < 1$, $\bar{x}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$, $\theta \in [0, 1]$, $\bar{\xi}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ and $\bar{\underline{x}}^{(0)} = \bar{x}^{(0)}$

Output: Sparse vector \bar{x}

- 1: Iterations($n \geq 0$): Update $\bar{x}^{(n)}$, $\bar{\xi}^{(n)}$, $\bar{\underline{x}}^{(n)}$ as follows:
 - 2: $\bar{\xi}^{(n+1)} = (\mathbf{I} + \sigma \partial F^*)^{-1}(\bar{\xi}^{(n)} + \sigma \Psi \bar{\underline{x}}^{(n)})$
 - 3: $\bar{x}^{(n+1)} = (\mathbf{I} + \tau \partial G)^{-1}(\bar{x}^{(n)} - \tau \Psi^H \bar{\xi}^{(n)})$
 - 4: $\bar{\underline{x}}^{(n+1)} = \bar{x}^{(n+1)} + \theta(\bar{x}^{(n+1)} - \bar{x}^{(n)})$
-

Line 3 of the Algorithm 4 adopts the proximal mapping:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{I} + \tau_{(n)} \partial G)^{-1}(\bar{u}) &= P_{\tau G}(\bar{u}) \\ &= \arg \min_{\bar{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}} \{ \tau G(\bar{x}) + \frac{1}{2} \|\bar{x} - \bar{u}\|_2^2 \} \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Which can be calculated by the shrinkage operations:

$$P_{\tau G}(u_i) = \begin{cases} u_i - \tau, & u_i \geq \tau \\ 0, & |u_i| \leq \tau \\ u_i + \tau, & u_i \leq -\tau \end{cases}$$

The proximal mapping of the line 2 is obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{I} + \sigma_{(n)} \partial F^*)^{-1}(\bar{p}) &= P_{\sigma F^*}(\bar{p}) \\ &= \arg \min_{\bar{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}} \{ \sigma F^*(\bar{x}) + \frac{1}{2} \|\bar{x} - \bar{p}\|_2^2 \} \\ &= \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + \sigma} (\bar{p} - \sigma \bar{y}) \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

An accelerated algorithm for solving the saddle-point problem can be achieved if G or F^* is uniformly convex [13].

$$\begin{aligned} \|\nabla F^*(\bar{x}) - \nabla F^*(\bar{z})\|_2 &= \|(y + \frac{1}{\gamma} \bar{x}) - (y + \frac{1}{\gamma} \bar{z})\|_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\gamma} \|\bar{x} - \bar{z}\|_2 \\ &\leq L \|\bar{x} - \bar{z}\|_2 \quad \text{s.t. } \exists L < \infty \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

Then F^* is uniformly convex and has a Lipschitz continuous gradient, and the accelerated algorithm is shown as follows.

Algorithm 5 Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual accelerated Algorithm

Input: $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times L}$, $\tau_0, \sigma_0 > 0$ simultaneously with $\tau_0 \sigma_0 L^2 \leq 1$, $\bar{x}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$, $\bar{\xi}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ and $\bar{x}^{(0)} = \bar{x}^{(0)}$.

Output: Sparsity vector \bar{x} .

1: Iterations($n \geq 0$): Update $\bar{x}^{(n)}, \bar{\xi}^{(n)}, \bar{x}^{(n)}, \theta_{(n)}, \tau_{(n)}, \sigma_{(n)}$ as follows:

2: $\bar{\xi}^{(n+1)} = (\mathbf{I} + \sigma_{(n)} \partial F^*)^{-1}(\bar{\xi}^{(n)} + \sigma_{(n)} \Phi \bar{x}^{(n)})$

3: $\bar{x}^{(n+1)} = (\mathbf{I} + \tau_{(n)} \partial G)^{-1}(\bar{x}^{(n)} - \tau_{(n)} \Phi^H \bar{\xi}^{(n)})$

4: $\theta_{(n)} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \sigma_{(n)}}$

5: $\tau_{(n+1)} = \theta_{(n)} \tau_{(n)}$

6: $\sigma_{(n+1)} = \sigma_{(k)} / \theta_{(n)}$

7: $\bar{x}^{(n+1)} = \bar{x}^{(n+1)} + \theta_{(n)} (\bar{x}^{(n+1)} - \bar{x}^{(n)})$

4 Comparison of the three Algorithms via the Donoho-Tanner graphs

A Donoho-Tanner graph is a two-dimensional plot used to evaluate the performance of a sparse recovery algorithm. The y -axis denoted as $\rho = s/m$, represents the ratio between the number of nonzero elements and the number of measurements. Besides, the x -axis $\delta = m/n$ is the undersampling rate, which describes the ratio between the number of measurements and length of the vector \vec{x} [14].

In order to generate the Donoho-Tanner graphs, an optimal measurement matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$ is constructed to be a Best Complex Antipodal Spherical Code(BCASC), which is known optimal in lower bound coherence [8]. Then the sparse n -dimensional signal \vec{x} is recovered from the measurements given by $\vec{y} = \mathbf{A}\vec{x}$. The l_2 recovery error $\|\vec{x} - \tilde{\vec{x}}\|_2$ is used for evaluating the performance of the algorithms and the estimation of the sparse signal $\tilde{\vec{x}}$ obtained by these three algorithms. The corresponding results are shown in the Donoho-Tanner graphs.

The two parameters $\delta = m/n$ and $\rho = s/m$ of the Donoho-Tanner graphs are within the range $0 \leq \delta \leq 1$, $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$. Utilizing the 16 equally-spaced discrete values of the two parameters, the different experimental cases are constituted. The l_2 recovery error is shown in the $\delta - \rho$ plane. For all experiments, the signal length is set to $n = 128$, and each pixel of the graphs presents the average values of 8 independent experiments.

Figures 2, 3 and 4 are the Donoho-Tanner graphs of normalized l_2 recovery error via OMP algorithm, Kalman filter and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm, respectively. Figures 5 and 6 show the results obtained for the convergence-accelerated algorithm of Kalman filter and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm.

Figure 2: Normalized sparse recovery error of Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)

In Figure 2, the four different threshold errors ($\epsilon = 10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}$ and 10^{-4}) are adopted in the OMP algorithm. The results demonstrate that, when the threshold error $\epsilon \leq 10^{-2}$, OMP shows good performance, and no obvious difference is observed with the decrease of the threshold error. Compared with the other two algorithms, the OMP algorithm displays the smallest failure region.

Figure 3: Normalized sparse recovery error of Kalman-Filter

In Figures 3, 4 and 5, the Donoho-Tanner graphs of normalized l_2 recovery error are obtained in accordance with 4 different number of iterations (250, 500, 1000 and 2000). As shown in Figures 3 and 4, both Kalman filter and Chambolle and Pock's primal dual algorithm always offer great performance regardless of the number of iterations.

Figure 4: Normalized sparse recovery error of Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

Figure 5: Normalized sparse recovery error of convergence-accelerated Kalman-Filter

For the convergence-accelerated Kalman filter, the normalized l_2 recovery error is demonstrated in Figure 5. With the increase of iteration times, the performance of convergence-accelerated Kalman-Filter has no obvious improvement. In addition, failure appears at some points for large iterations.

Figure 6: Normalized sparse recovery error of convergence-accelerated Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

The Donoho-Tanner graphs of convergence-accelerated Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm are demonstrated in Figure 6. We set the parameter $\gamma = 100, 50, 10$ and 1 of this algorithm to observe the changes of normalized l_2 recovery error. The result shows that, with the decrease of the γ , the error increased. In addition, when the γ is less than 1 , the error will exceed the predefined value.

In order to better understand the influence of acceleration, 10000 iterations were performed to observe the recovered amplitude value in Figure 7, where $\gamma = 10000, 100, 50, 10, 1, 0.1$ and 0.01 .

Figure 7: Amplitude variation for different parameter γ

Figure 7 shows that when $\gamma \geq 10$, the algorithm can not converge to a correct value within 10000 iterations. As the parameter γ is reduced to 1, 0.1 and 0.01 respectively, amplitude converges to a true value of about 175. However, when $\gamma = 1$, it shows a slow convergence speed, and when $\gamma = 0.01$, a large overshooting appears. Compared with other parameters, at $\gamma = 0.1$, the algorithm can quickly converge to the correct value, while ensuring a lower overshoot. Then $\gamma = 0.1$ will be used for the acceleration.

5 Results for ToF Depth Imaging

In order to retrieve correct depth and amplitude data from real data effected by multipath interference (MPI), 7 equally-spaced frequencies $\omega = n\omega_0$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) in the range of 0-120 MHz, each 20 MHz apart, are transmitted from the camera. According to the equation (12) the measurement \vec{y} is obtained:

$$\vec{y} = [y_0, y_{20}, \dots, y_{120}]^\top \quad (50)$$

On the basis of the equation (11) and (13) the vector \vec{y} can be expressed as $\vec{y} = \Psi \vec{x} + \vec{\sigma}$. To recover the sparse vector \vec{x} , a sensing matrix $\Psi \in \mathbb{C}^{7 \times 150}$ is generated as follows:

$$\Psi = \begin{pmatrix} e^{j0 \times \frac{2\pi \times 1}{L}} & e^{j0 \times \frac{2\pi \times 2}{L}} & \dots & e^{j0 \times \frac{2\pi \times L}{L}} \\ e^{j1 \times \frac{2\pi \times 1}{L}} & e^{j1 \times \frac{2\pi \times 2}{L}} & \dots & e^{j1 \times \frac{2\pi \times L}{L}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ e^{j(N-1) \times \frac{2\pi \times 1}{L}} & e^{j(N-1) \times \frac{2\pi \times 2}{L}} & \dots & e^{j(N-1) \times \frac{2\pi \times L}{L}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (51)$$

where $L = 150$ means the number of discrete depth steps, k represents the index of steps ranging from 0 to 150. $N = 7$ expresses the number of the equally-spaced frequencies.

Inputting the measurement vector \vec{y} and sensing matrix Ψ into the algorithms, the amplitude A_k , and its position k in sparse vector \vec{x} are obtained. With the location information, the phases ϕ_n can be calculated:

$$\phi_n = \frac{2\pi \times k}{L} \times n \quad (52)$$

Here n is kept in the range between 0 and 6, which means different frequencies. With the equation (3), the distance information is expressed as:

$$d = \frac{c\phi_n}{2 \times 2\pi f_1 \times n} \quad (53)$$

where c is the speed of light, and f_1 is the base frequency.

The experiment is set up as shown in Figure 8. The farthest to the left is the ToF camera featuring a ToF imaging chip from pmdtechnologies AG. In the middle, two panels are located in front of the camera, of which the left is quite transparent, and this panel is 20cm away from the camera. The other one is 25cm away from the camera, which is translucent and produces a stronger scattering. The farthest to the right of the ToF camera is a white panel, which keeps the distance of 0.75m from the camera.

Figure 8: Experiment setup

Through experiments, two kinds of data are extracted. For the first data, we conduct 50 times measuring, the average value of them is collected. The second data is more accurate. The average value comprises 100 measurements and the same averaged measurements were acquired ten times. The three algorithms and the two accelerated algorithms are applied to the first real data. The depth and amplitude map for the most prominent bounce are reconstructed as follows:

Figure 9: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via OMP

Figure 10: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via Kalman-Filter

Figure 11: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

For the OMP algorithm, the iteration threshold error is set at $\epsilon = 10^{-2}$, the iteration times of the Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm and Kalman filter algorithm are set at 10^3 .

It can be seen from the Figure 9-13 that all algorithms can generate depth maps very well. Nevertheless, in the center area of the depth map, that is to say, in the area with strong light intensity, these algorithms show different performance at the translucent and transparent panel.

From the Figure 9 and 11, a similar performance is shown by OMP algorithm and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm. In the top left corner of the translucent panel, there is a color gradient from blue color to aqua, of which blue indicates that the distance between the translucent panel and camera is 0.25m, and the aqua indicates that the distance to the white panel is 0.75m. This color gradient from blue to aqua means a distance increasing process from 0.25 to 0.75m and the step size is 5cm, which depends on the discretization degree of depth domain [15]. However, these distances between 0.25 and 0.75m do not actually exist, but are an artifact caused by the influence of multipath interference. In the right middle of the transparent panel, light blue appears in a few areas, which is also caused by multipath interference.

Figure 12: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via convergence accelerated Kalman-Filter

Figure 13: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via convergence accelerated Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

From the Figure 10 and 13, similar performance is shown by Kalman filter and convergence-accelerated Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm. Although there is no color gradient at the top left corner of translucent panel, two color taps, green and aquamarine, appear in the peripheral area of the corner, indicate the distances of 0.8 and 0.7 m. Compared with the ground truth of 0.75m, small errors appear. Compared with the first two algorithms, Kalman filter and convergence-accelerated Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm show larger error area on both translucent and transparent panel, which is caused by the multipath inference.

According to the previous comparison, the convergence-accelerated Kalman filter shows best performance. There is neither color gradient nor color taps at the top left of the translucent panel. Only a few error points exist in the right middle of the transparent panel. Compared with other algorithms, fewer areas are caused by the multipath interference.

Figure 14: Amplitude variation versus iteration number for the three algorithms

With regard to amplitude map, all three algorithms can generate good observation images. However, there are significant differences in the amplitude values. The reason lies in the number of iterations of 10^3 . The amplitude value generated by the Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm, Kalman filter, and their accelerated algorithms do not reach the convergence value. To estimate which algorithm has greater performance in reconstructed amplitude value, the amplitude variation of the same random pixel is measured. At the same time, the iteration times of the Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm and Kalman filter are extended to 10^4 . The results are shown in Figure 14.

In the right image of the Figure 14, the OMP algorithm only run for two iterations. The amplitude value stabilizes at around 210. The left image shows the changing curve of the Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm, Kalman filter, and their accelerated algorithms. After 3000 iterations, the amplitude of the two accelerated algorithms tends to stabilize and finally converge to approximately the same value of 175. However, the two non-accelerated algorithms converge to smaller non-optimal values after 1000 iterations.

In the same way, another set of measurements at different frequencies are input into the three algorithms. The results are shown in Figures 15-20. Comparing the corresponding depth map and amplitude map with the previous, there is no significant difference. The amplitude image delivered by the OMP algorithm exhibits lower variability, while there are no significant differences among the amplitude images delivered by other algorithms.

Figure 15: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via OMP

Figure 16: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via Kalman-Filter

Figure 17: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

Figure 18: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via convergence accelerated Kalman-Filter

Figure 19: Reconstructed depth map and amplitude map via convergence accelerated Chambolle and Pock's Primal-Dual Algorithm

Figure 20: Amplitude variation versus iteration number for the three algorithms

6 Conclusions

Compressed sensing is a valid method of addressing multipath interference. In this paper, three sparse recovery algorithms, OMP, Kalman filter, and Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm, are applied to retrieve depth and amplitude maps for the dominant bounce from multiple frequency measurements. Apart from OMP, which had been previously tested, Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm is as outstanding as OMP algorithm in reconstructing depth information. In comparison with Chambolle and Pock's primal-dual algorithm, its convergence-accelerated algorithm does not achieve a good improvement. Compared with other algorithms, the convergence-accelerated Kalman filter shows the smallest error areas, which are caused by the multipath interference. In terms of computational complexity, OMP has great advantage over the other algorithms.

Future work includes applying and modifying these algorithms for eliminating and mitigating the multipath for a wide variety of scenes.

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